

Synthesis of some New Bio-active Aryl Amides

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SEVERAL *N*-acylated derivatives of pyrazole, morpholine and imidazole were synthesised (1-3) using substituted phenoxyacetyl chlorides (Scheme 1) and screened for their anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory and fungicidal activities.

X = Substituent; HET = heterocycles

(1a - k)

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| 1a ; R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H | 1g ; R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =NO ₂ |
| b ; R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =Br | h ; R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂ , R ₃ =H |
| c ; R ₁ =R ₂ =Br, R ₃ =H | i ; R ₁ =R ₂ =NO ₂ , R ₃ =H |
| d ; R ₁ =R ₂ =Br, R ₃ =H | j ; R ₁ =NO ₂ , R ₂ =R ₃ =H |
| e ; R ₁ =Br, R ₂ =R ₃ =H | k ; R ₁ =R ₂ =H, R ₃ =NO ₂ |
| f ; R ₁ =R ₂ =H, R ₃ =Br | |

NOTES

(2a-e)

- 2a : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{NO}_2$
 b : $R_1 = R_2 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_3 = \text{H}$
 c : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_2 = \text{H}$
 d : $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 e : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$

(3a-e)

- 3a : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{NO}_2$
 b : $R_1 = R_2 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_3 = \text{H}$
 c : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_2 = \text{H}$
 d : $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 e : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$

Structures of the compounds have been confirmed by their elemental analyses, ir and ^1H nmr spectra. Their ir spectra showed the principal absorptions at 2877–2888 (CH), 1638–1648 (C=O), 1585–1590 (CN), 1496–1508 (nitro group attached to phenyl ring) and 1025–1045 cm^{-2} (Ar–O–) respectively. Their ^1H nmr spectra displayed the following signals: 1a δ 8.20–8.40, 7.50, 6.25, 3.50; 1e, 1f, 1j, 1k, 2d, 2e, 3d, 3e δ 8.30–8.60, 7.70, 7.50, 7.15, 6.30, 3.65, 3.50, 2.90, 2.70; 1c, 1d, 1h, 1i, 2b, 2c, 3b, 3c δ 8.60, 8.50, 8.30, 7.70, 7.50, 7.15, 6.30, 3.60, 3.50, 2.90, 2.70; 1h, 1g, 2a, 3a δ 8.40–8.50, 7.70, 7.55, 7.10, 6.25, 3.65, 3.55, 3.50, 2.65, 2.70.

The compounds were screened for various biological activities.

Biological activities : Anthelmintic activity was evaluated following Watkins method¹. Nitrophenoxyacetylpyrazoles (1g–k) showed greater activity than bromophenoxyacetylpyrazoles. The trinitrophenoxyacetylpyrazole showed the most significant activity.

Anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated by carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method² and the percent inhibition of inflammation after 5 h was calculated³. Compounds 2a–e did not show significant inhibition, and 2d and 2e showed only a mild activity (18.75 and 21.87%, respectively) as compared to standard ibuprofen (71.87% inhibition).

Fungicidal activity was evaluated by the method of Raper *et al.*⁴ *in vitro* against the organisms, *Aspergillus niger*, *A. fumigatus*, *Candida albicans* and *Curvularia lunata* and the amount of growth inhibition was calculated. Nitrophenoxyacetyl-imidazoles (3a–e) exhibited good fungicidal activity. However, as the number of nitro groups in the phenyl ring increased, the activity was found to

decrease. Compound 3e showed significant activity against all the fungi tested.

Experimental

Aryloxyacetic acids : To a mixture of the phenol and/or related phenols (1 g) and 33% NaOH (3.5 ml) was added 50% chloroacetic acid (2.5 ml) followed by a little water to dissolve the sodium salt of phenols and the mixture was heated gently on a water-bath for ~1 h. After cooling the solution was diluted with water (50 ml), acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with ether. After washing with water, the ether layer was evaporated to yield the various phenoxyacetic acids.

Aryloxyacetyl chlorides : A mixture of aryloxyacetic acids and excess of thionyl chloride, was refluxed for 8 h on a water-bath. Excess of thionyl chloride was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with organic solvent(s) to afford the products.

Aryloxyacetylpyrazole/morpholine/imidazole : To a mixture of ice-cold solution of pyrazole (0.052 mol), morpholine (0.042 mol) or imidazole (0.045 mol) in benzene (30 ml) and 4N NaOH (5 ml) was added dropwise in the aryloxyacetyl chloride with constant stirring for about 60 min. The separated amides were filtered, washed and purified over a column of silica gel and/or neutral alumina using various organic solvents as eluant. The amides were finally crystallised from different organic solvent(s) : 1a (yield 68%), m.p. 113–15°; 1b (70), 82°; 1c (71), 112°; 1d (65), 168°; 1e (68), 220–22°; 1f (59), 118°; 1g (71), 173°; 1h (67), 151–52°; 1i (65), 185°; 1j (63), 163°; 1k (65), 177°; 2a (68), 178–80°; 2b (71), 113–14°; 2c (65), 140–42°; 2d (70), 201–02°; 2e (78), 228–30°; 3a (62), 114–16°; 3b (62), 216–18°; 3c (58), 222°; 3d (58), 190–92°; 3e (65), 202°; all compounds gave satisfactory Br analysis.

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